

**THE IMPACT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE
ON ACCOUNTING MEASURES OF FINANCIAL
PERFORMANCE, TRADE OPENNESS, LIABILITIES
AND CREDIT USAGE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON
TURKISH SMSs ***

Doç. Dr. Tamer AKSOY **
Sezer BOZKUŞ ***

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the literature on corporate governance (CG) by providing additional evidence on the impact of CG on accounting measures of financial performance, liabilities and credit usage, trade openness by observing firm performance in emerging economies, concentrating on the Turkish experience, a part of the world that has been a good sample of emerging economies in the literature and also, to our knowledge, this is the first study on the KOSGEB database in Turkey.

Using a sample of 47.053 Turkish small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) firms data taken from KOSGEB, and based on the variables firm size, legal status, liabilities and credit usage, concentrated ownership and exports we test the relationship in determining the level of financial performance, trade openness and especially CG. The logit model is used as the methodology and based on the empirical findings we make some policy recommendations and note the key issues for further studies.

Key Words: Corporate Governance, SMEs, Liabilities and Credit Usage, Financial Performance, Trade Openness, Logit Model

JEL Classification Codes: G34, M40, G32, M14

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**Assoc. Prof.Dr., CPA, CFE, TOBB University of Economics and Technology, Business Administration Dept.,

E-mail: drtameraksoy@gmail.com

*** CPA, CFE, CIA, CISA, KPMG Advisory Services, sbotzkus@kpmg.com

KÜRESEL ¹ FINANSAL KRİZ ORTAMINDA KURUMSAL YÖNETİMİN FINANSAL PERFORMANS, TICARI AÇIKLIK, YABANCI KAYNAK VE KREDİ KULLANIMINA İLİŞKİN MUHASEBESEL ÖLÇÜTLER ÜZERİNDEKİ ETKİSİ: TÜRKİYE'DEKİ KOBİ'LERE YÖNELİK AMPİRİK BİR İNCELEME

ÖZET

Kurumsal yönetim (KY) yaklaşımı, sadece gelişmiş ülke ekonomileri için değil, özellikle gelişen ülke ekonomileri açısından daha fazla önem taşımaktadır. Çünkü bu ülkelerin finansal kurumları ve altyapıları, Kurumsal yönetim ilkelerini uygulamada yetersizdir. Literatürde kurumsal yönetim mekanizmasını açıklayan iki yaklaşım bulunmaktadır. Bunlar içsel ve dışsal yaklaşımlardır.

İçsel kurumsal yönetim mekanizması genel olarak işletmelerin ortaklık yapısı, yönetim kurulunun işleyişi ile yönetim organizasyonu gibi konuları kapsarken; dışsal kurumsal yönetim mekanizması ise, sermaye piyasaları ile yasal ve kurumsal sistemlerin izlenmesini içermektedir.

Çalışmamızın amacı, KOBİ'lerin Kurumsal yönetim performansı incelenerek gelişen ülkeler açısından kurumsal yönetim literatürüne katkı sağlamaktır. Türkiye'deki KOBİ finansal performansları ışığında homojenlik gösteren ve ülkelerarası kıyas kısıtı olmayan bir çalışma amaçlanmıştır. Bu çalışma; Türkiye'de yoğun gelişme ve yasal düzenlemelerin yaşandığı 'geçiş' döneminde gerçekleştirilmesi, seçilen değişkenlere ilişkin KOBİ'lerle doğrudan ilgili KOSGEB verilerini Türkiye'de kullanan "ilk" çalışma olması ve politika yapıcılara ve kurumsal yönetimle ilgili taraflara öneriler sunması sebebiyle önem taşımaktadır.

KOSGEB üyesi 47.053 firmanın verileri ve logit modeli kullanılarak, büyüklük, yasal statü, yabancı kaynak, kredi

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kullanımı, şirket sahipliği, ticaret, ihracat durumları gibi temel bilgilere, muhasebesel ölçütlere dayanarak KOBİ'lerin finansal performansı ile kurumsal yönetim anlayışı arasındaki ilişki ampirik test edilmiştir. Çalışmada, KY literatürü, veriler, kullanılan logit modelleri yöntemi, örnekleme, model seçimi ve bulgular açıklanmış ve politika önerilerinde bulunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kurumsal Yönetim, KOBİ, Yabancı Kaynak ve Kredi kullanımı, Finansal Performans, Ticari açıklık, Logit Model

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1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance is consistent with the philosophy and the practices of a free market and a democratic culture all over the world. It gives the final authority and complete responsibility to a board of directors whose decision-making responsibility is mutually respectful and participatory where independent and outside views are valued. The corporate governance mechanism suggests that board maximizes shareholder value through fairness, accountability and transparency.

In emerging markets, where ownership is concentrated and institutional infrastructure is usually weak, corporate governance issues can not be basically explained by agency problems. The controlling shareholder commonly takes an active role in running the company and holds executive positions to be more powerful.

The material characteristics of a country, and its own governance policies that influence the common business "environment," can also have a main impact on firms' ability to accomplish its trade and industry potential. Globalization of firms in transition economies has dramatically changed the boundaries and content of governance and strategy of firms exposing them to several

competitive pressures. Sanders and Carpenter (1998) discuss that managers of these kinds of firms ought to make strategic decisions in the complex decision-making environment, and one should expect that the performance of large firms may be closely linked with managerial flexibility in making strategic decisions within the context of the firm's corporate governance.

Yet the corporate governance * issue remains relatively unexplored. Emphasis on organizational and environmental factors as antecedents of both financial performance and export performance ignores possible organizational effects of managers' strategic independence. Newman (2000) defined managers' strategic independence as their autonomy in strategic decision making and absence of direct interference and constraints imposed by the owners. In this way, these situations enable the managers to provide timely and effective strategic responses in a speedily changing environment (Harrigan, 1985; Mahoney, 1995). On the other hand, although preceding research suggests that this may be a significant antecedent of managerial ability to undertake performance-enhancing strategies, there is little known about the impact of emerging corporate governance mechanisms on managerial strategic independence, liabilities volume and trade openness (Hoskisson *et al.*, 2000).

The major perspective adopted in this paper is that well-functioning, market-based systems of corporate governance provide the important business decisions in the hands of professional managers, while owners make managers accountable by using various governance mechanisms, such as board monitoring, reporting and internal control. In contrast, Balassa (1982) (1983) argues that inadequate managerial independence in the emerging countries driven by the characteristics of the legal framework of corporate governance, may have negative

*For further information on corporate governance issues, please refer to Robert and the others (2008)

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implications for firm performance.

In the same way, this study explores the links between corporate governance, managers' strategic independence, financial performance and export performance of small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) in an economically important transition country, i.e. Turkey. Before Turkey's economic reforms, exporting remained the monopoly of a handful of specialized state-owned companies. Turkey is currently undergoing an IMF-sponsored restructuring process. This is achieved after experiencing high and persistent inflation but relatively high growth for more than two decades.

Despite a constructive outlook at the end of 2000, the Turkish economy was fallen into the deepest economic crises of its history in early 2001. Due to rising unemployment and the high proportion of a young labor force in Turkey, there is limited capital accumulation in the financial markets and also the importance of foreign direct investment flows have become a major thrust for economic stability and prosperity in Turkey.

As a transition and emerging economy, Turkey builds a tough regulatory structure for corporate governance, which rests mainly upon a public enforcement model, with the Capital Markets Board (CMB) which is the chief Authority in setting corporate governance standards for publicly held companies, for enforcing the applicable standards and for fostering market integrity in Turkey. CMB is also in an effort to construct a corporate governance index to rate companies based on their adherence to the CMB's corporate governance principles introduced in 2003. In cooperation with the Turkish corporate governance principles and the decision of CMB on 7th Feb 2005, Istanbul Stock Exchange ("ISE") introduced the corporate governance index ** principles.

** For further information on CG and corporate governance index (CGI) in connection with the modern internal auditing, international auditing standards, corporate governance rating scores and the listed companies in İSE (İMKB) corporate governance index, please refer to AKSOY (2010:196-209)

The formation of the index will augment the market pressure to put investors back in control of companies, creating a corporate culture of transparency.

It has been acknowledged in previous research that corporate governance affects enterprises restructuring and financial performance (Hoskisson *et al.*, 2000; Peng, 2004), while the effects of governance on exporting are less clear. Therefore, transition economies are a natural context to test theories concerning the first stage of internationalization, i.e. direct exporting as a sign of trade openness (Andersen, 1993; Aulakh *et al.*, 2000).

Keesing (1967) grants valuable information regarding the reason why trade has positive industrialization and development effects. Trade is an important channel that brings individuals in developing countries into contact with new technologies, products and skills. In this way these learning effects generate an outward shift of the production-possibility frontier.

Luo and Peng (1999) state that in the liberalized economic environment, with slow-moving internal demand, adopting export-oriented strategies may be closely linked to better financial performance of the firms.

International trades also present resources whereby some countries can avoid the natural limitations of their own domestic markets. Production for export can expand employment opportunities for firms. Keesing (1967) argues that this may have similar effects in industries with forward or backward linkages to the export sector. Increased struggle among multinational firms can also decline the monopoly position of some domestic enterprises and result in lesser prices and improved service for consumers. In addition trade openness can also create important continuing benefits if foreign competition forces local producers to modernize and follow up new developments and technologies within their industry.

Balassa (1971), and Grubel and Johnson (1971) illustrate how the level and structure of a country's own trade barriers may

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incorporate an important anti-export bias. Balassa (1982)(1983) determined that countries which pursued “outward oriented” trade policies, characterized by low import barriers were better able to react to adverse external shocks than those with high tariffs.

Our study makes a number of contributions. We provide a new framework modelling the linkages between managers’ strategic independence, corporate governance factors, and trade openness via exporting, liabilities and credit usage and financial performance. Research in this area has been thin and a major barrier has been the complex interdependence of governance, strategies and performance.

The import protection and export promotion through monopolistic, state-owned foreign trade companies meant that enterprises were ill equipped to meet overseas threats. Liberalization and privatization were designed to abolish the constraints on the independent managerial decision-making process imposed by state ownership and the command-economy system (Hoskisson et al., 2000; Makhija, 2004). In the case of Turkey, companies were privatized using a wide range of methods, with a significant participation of institutional corporate investors, including multinationals (Djankov and Murrell, 2002). These privatizations resulted in a diverse range of ownership structures and corporate governance mechanisms (Newman, 2000).

Our study is based on the strategic management perspective, with export intensity and financial performance being the outcome of a multi-dimensional strategic decision making process. This process is driven by the firm’s managers’ strategic independence, which is defined as “an ability to respond to various demands from dynamic competitive environments” (Sanchez, 1995, p. 138). When managers are not constrained by owners in terms of their strategic decisions, they are able to take timely actions aimed at improving the firm’s competitive position in domestic markets and promoting overseas outputs (Aulakh *et al.*, 2000).

By being involved in international activities, firms in transition economies may build up further their capabilities (Sanders and Carpenter, 1998), and this suggests a positive relationship between exporting as a good sign of trade openness, liabilities and credit usage and financial performance (Luo and Peng, 1999).

International business research argues that internationalization enables firms to leverage their existing capabilities and knowledge across countries and create scale economies otherwise unavailable domestically (Andersen, 1993). Sanders and Carpenter (1988) suggest that being exposed to overseas markets helps the firm to respond more effectively to foreign competitors in their domestic market. Firms are continually searching for new technologies, new ways of organizing their operation, and firms can take advantage of new information gained by exporting that is also valuable when competing in their home market (Bernard and Jensen, 1999).

Gains from export orientation may be particularly strong in transition economies, where firms could face limited opportunities at home ('push factor'). More importantly, given the low level of international trade, substantial gains can result from taking advantage of external liberalization and export orientation ('pull factor'). Luo and Peng, (1999) argue that the latter could become a key factor leading to improved financial performance. Hence export orientation is positively associated with financial performance.

The composition of a firm's board of directors is another governance parameter that can affect the decision-making process, shaping the extent of managers' strategic independence (Baysinger and Hoskisson, 1990).

Although performance and export orientation in particular may be increased by higher degrees of managerial decision-making autonomy, the latter, in turn, depend on the firm's governance factors such as ownership structure and board composition (Uhlenbruck *et al.*, 2003; Hoskisson *et al.*, 2000).

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Therefore, our framework suggests that the complex relationships between governance, liabilities volume, liabilities and credit usage, exporting performance and financial performance *** are mediated by managers' strategic independence. The following sections discuss these issues in detail.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Turkish SME firm data is taken from Turkish Small and Medium Industry Development Organization (KOSGEB). There are 47.063 small and medium-sized enterprises in this analysis all over Turkey. The descriptive statistics of these variables are shown in the Table 1 as follows:

The founding year for small and medium-sized enterprises in Turkey is mostly concentrated within the period of 1990-1999 as of %43 and then the period 2000-2007 follows with % 29. The %52 of small and medium-sized enterprises are established as limited companies and, %30 of small and medium-sized enterprises are belongs to real persons in Turkey. The schooling level of almost all (%99,97) small and medium-sized enterprises managers are graduated from primary or secondary school. Similarly, almost all small and medium-sized enterprises are managed by the owners and only %00.2 of small and medium-sized enterprises are managed by the professionals in Turkey.

The amount of capital small and medium-sized enterprises have is mostly concentrated (%99,97) within the range of 50 million TL and below. The majority (%91,82) of labor force of Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises is classified as 49 or below. The % 38 of small and medium-sized enterprises have a corporate web page.

The liabilities and credit usages of small and medium-sized enterprises are about % 35 and %75 of small and medium-sized

*** For further information on the performance of SMEs, please refer to (Lu and Beamish 2001)

enterprises have new investment decisions for near future plans. The Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises use credit typically because of lack of working capital. There are only %23 of small and medium-sized enterprises are able to export what they produce. The quality certificates are not that widespread among small and medium-sized enterprises in Turkey. There are only %13,67 of them have TSE, %7,55 of them have ISO9000 and %1,97 CE respectively.

Based on the findings of Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises as shown in Table 1, it takes time to set up corporate governance structure and difficult to transform the habits of owners. Although the small and medium-sized enterprises have the largest share in the Turkish Economy, they are unaware of the importance of corporate governance and BASEL principles at all. Furthermore, the implementation of IFRS (international financial reporting standards) for small and medium-sized enterprises will be costly and time-consuming in Turkey. Since the greater parts of managers are graduated from primary or secondary school, there is a vital need for teaching and awareness campaigns supported by the regulatory authorities in Turkey.

The logistic models are used to establish and analyze the factors affecting the trade openness and corporate governance in Turkey. The concept of trade openness has been indicated in the model as proxy variable by using export performance of firms in Turkey. The information regarding the firms' exporting operations (EXPORT) exist or not is taken as a dependent variable in the model.

Logistic regression analysis is an accepted method of reporting social research results based on the analysis of data with a dichotomous dependent variable. The reasons why logistic regression models are preferred rather than using simple linear regression (OLS) analysis is explained in the literature by various authors such as Aldrich and Nelson, (1984); Hanushek and

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Jackson, (1977); Maddala, (1983). Regarding the OLS analysis, there are some major difficulties noted by DeMaris (1995).

The first one is the use of a linear function, with the assumption of independence between the predictors and the error term, and error heteroskedasticity, or non-constant variance of the errors across combinations of predictor values. In brief, applying a linear function is challenging because it leads to predicted probabilities outside the choice of 0 to 1.

Basically, the normal and logistic distributions are suitably alike in shape that the choice of distribution is not in fact important. Hence, the substantive conclusions reached by using logistic regression should be identical. On the other hand, the logistic distribution is advantageous in practice due to its mathematical tractability and interpretability. The mathematical advantage of the logit formulation is apparent in the ability to express the probability that $Y = 1$ as a closed-form expression:

$$P(Y = 1) = \pi = \frac{\exp(\alpha + \sum \beta_k X_k)}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \sum \beta_k X_k)} \quad (1)$$

In that the exponential function (exp) always results in a number between 0 and infinity, it is obvious that the right-hand side of Equation 1 above is always bounded between 0 and 1. To write the right-hand side of Equation 1 as an additive function of the predictors, we use a logit transformation on the probability π . The logit transformation is $\log [\pi / (1 - \pi)]$, where log refers to the natural logarithm. The term $\pi / (1 - \pi)$ is called the odds, and is a ratio of probabilities. The log odds can be any number between minus and plus infinity. It can therefore be modeled as a linear function of our predictor set. In this way, the logistic regression model can be written as follows:

$$\log\left(\frac{\pi}{1 - \pi}\right) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_k X_k \quad (2)$$

DeMaris (1995) notes that the maximum likelihood estimates have desirable properties, one of which is that, in large samples, the regression coefficients are approximately normally distributed. This makes it possible to test each coefficient for significance using a z test.

3. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Depending on the KOSGEB data of small and medium-sized enterprises all over Turkey, the key variables affecting the exporting is explained as follows:

1. the legal status of small and medium-sized enterprises (CORPORATION, REAL, LIMITED, OTHER),
2. the labor force (LABOR)
3. the usage of investment credit (INVESTMENTCRD)
4. the usage of working capital credit **** (WORKINGCAPCRD)
5. the usage of credit guarantee fund (CGFUND)
6. the usage of collateral credit (COLLATERALCRD)
7. the usage of open credit (OPENCRD)
8. new investment plan (NEWINVPLN)

Parallel to the relevant literature explained above, EXPORT variable is used as a proxy variable to explain the impact of corporate governance on trade openness in Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises. The model is shown in the Table 2.

Based on the empirical findings shown in the Table 2, there is an inverse relationship between EXPORT and LABOR. This is not surprising for Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises because the more the size of the firms increase the more they become capital-oriented operations. Needless to say, considering the economies of scale for the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises, the inverse relationship is supported by the theory.

In addition, there is a positive relationship between EXPORT and

**** For further information on the effect of working capital management on SME profitability please refer to Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano (2007)

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CORPORATION, INVESTMENTCRD, WORKINGCAPCRD,
CGFUND, COLLATERALCRD, OPENCRD, NEWINVPLN.

The trade openness leads to an increase in the level of internationalization and integration to the capital markets for the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises. Hence, these firms are also enforced to compete with the firms all over the world to gain advantage for achieving exports.

The important point is that the legal status is also a significant factor impacting on the trade openness and it is also a sign of governance policies available at the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises. Compared to other, real, or limited companies, corporations are more likely to establish corporate governance mechanisms at work. This empirical finding is also supported by the literature.

Since Turkey is an emerging country, there is always a need for credit support to improve the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises. Therefore, the positive relationship between the liabilities and credit usage of various types, i.e. NVESTMENTCRD, WORKINGCAPCRD, CGFUND, COLLATERALCRD, OPENCRD that small and medium-sized enterprises have and EXPORT is as we expected. The Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises usually make new investment plans based on their future strategies to gain more experience, improve their skills and increase their capacity in their own sector. This process is also directly related to the corporate governance and the trade openness issues of the SMEs.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of small and medium-sized enterprises in Turkey (continued)

web page	average	standard deviation	liabilities and credit usage	average	standard deviation
Yes	38%	0.486	yes	35%	0.475
No	62%	0.514	no	65%	0.525
Export	average	standard deviation	type of credit	average	standard deviation
Yes	23%	0.419	working capital credit	25.90%	0.438
No	77%	0.581	investment credit	7.66%	0.266
			export credit	4.37%	0.204
quality certificates	average	standard deviation	collateral credit	18.64%	0.389
ISO9000	7.55%	0.264	guarantee credit	7.99%	0.271
ISO14000	0.35%	0.059	credit guarantee fund	0.27%	0.052
HACCP	0.93%	0.096	open credit	10.22%	0.303
TSE	13.67%	0.344			
CE	average	standard deviation	new investment	average	standard deviation
ISO1649	0.27%	0.052	yes	75%	0.431
			no	25%	0.569

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Table 2: The impact of corporate governance on accounting measures of financial performance, liabilities and credit usage and trade openness - Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises

Convergence in 4 Iterations. Final criterion was 0.0000000
 ≤ 0.0000100

Dependent Variable	EXPORT
Usable Observations	47063
Degrees of Freedom	47056
Log Likelihood	-29946.378464
Average Likelihood	0.5292449
Pseudo-R**2	0.0498903
Log Likelihood(Base)	-31127.670156
LR Test of Coefficients(6)	2362.5834
Significance Level of LR	0.0000000

Variable	Coeff	Std Error	T-Stat	Significance
1. LABOR	-0.261	0.005	-48.629	0.000
2. INVESTMENTCRD	0.180	0.037	4.750	0.000
3. COLLATERALCRD	0.395	0.0255	15.456	0.000
4. CORPORATION	0.886	0.0280	31.590	0.000
5. CGFUND	0.459	0.185	2.479	0.013
6. OPENCRD	0.624	0.032	19.471	0.000
7. NEWINVPLN	0.300	0.023	12.982	0.000

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the empirical findings for the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), there is a relationship between the firms' level of liabilities and credit usage, financial performance, trade openness and corporate governance implementations. This issue will become essential for the Turkish small and medium-

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sized enterprises in the near future since there will be a change in the Commercial Code in Turkey. The new Commercial Code will bring new rules and regulations related to corporate governance framework and legal status of organizations. The international financial reporting standards (IFRS-UFRS) will be an obligation for all the firms in Turkey after the new Commercial Code (TTK).

Considering the fact that there is deep financial crisis in the world economy, including Turkey, firms should be more efficient and profitable to survive in the markets. In order to be more efficient and profitable, the corporate governance can be recommended as critical success factors for the firms. In addition, there is a positive and significant impact of corporate governance and governance factors on the trade openness which we have tested on the Turkish case.

In conclusion, the impact of corporate governance is measured by the legal status of firms, i.e. corporations, new investment plans and various credit types of the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises. These variables are taken as a proxy to determine the corporate governance approaches of the Turkish small and medium-sized enterprises.

Hence, we note that these proxy variables are statistically significant to prove and conclude that there is a positive impact of corporate governance on accounting measures of financial performance and exports, i.e. trade openness in Turkey.

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